

Prime Number Sequence Within Even Numbers

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Abstract

In this paper, sequence of prime numbers would be investigated in even numbers.

1 Understanding

Assuming that for prime number p :

$$\forall p = (n^3 + 3n^2 + 2n)p' + p'' \quad (n \in \mathbb{N})$$

By assuming two primes:

$$\begin{aligned} p_a &= (n^3 + 3n^2 + 2n)p_b + p_c \\ p_d &= (m^3 + 3m^2 + 2m)p_e + p_f \end{aligned}$$

Goldbach's conjecture[1] assumes that:

$$p_a + p_d = 2k \Rightarrow p_g + p_h = p_a + p_d + 2 = (2k + 2), \exists p_g, \exists p_h$$

As expanding the equation:

$$\begin{aligned} p_a + p_d &= (n^3 + 3n^2 + 2n)p_b + p_c + (m^3 + 3m^2 + 2m)p_e + p_f \\ \Rightarrow p_a + p_d + 2 &= (n^3 + 3n^2 + 2n)p_b + p_c + (m^3 + 3m^2 + 2m)p_e + p_f + 2 \\ &= p_g + p_h \end{aligned}$$

Assuming that:

$$q + r = 2 \quad (q \in \mathbb{Z}, r \in \mathbb{Z}, q > -p_a, q > -p_d, r > -p_a, r > -p_d)$$

Again, assuming that $\mathbb{P}$ is a prime number set, and Goldbach's conjecture could be:

$$\begin{aligned} &(n^3 + 3n^2 + 2n)p_b + p_c + (m^3 + 3m^2 + 2m)p_e + p_f + q + r \\ \Rightarrow &(n^3 + 3n^2 + 2n)p_b + p_c + q \in \mathbb{P}, (m^3 + 3m^2 + 2m)p_e + p_f + r \in \mathbb{P}, \exists q, \exists r \end{aligned}$$

As with assumption of prime number sequence, at least $q \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ or $r \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$. If there are no cases with $(n^3 + 3n^2 + 2n)p_b + p_c + q$ and $(m^3 + 3m^2 + 2m)p_e + p_f + r$ that fulfills the condition, than Goldbach's conjecture would be wrong. But as for listing:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall q = 2 &\Rightarrow r = 0, \\ \forall r = 2 &\Rightarrow q = 0, \\ \forall q = 1 &\Rightarrow r = 1, \\ \forall r = 1 &\Rightarrow q = 1 \end{aligned}$$

And by for all conditions when $(q = 1$ with $r = 1)$ or $(q = 0$ with $r = 2)$ or $(q = 2$ with $r = 0)$, Goldbach's conjecture is always true.

2 Conclusion

Goldbach's conjecture is true.

References

- [1] P. H. Fuss, *Correspondance mathématique et physique de quelques célèbres géometres du XVIIIème siècle*, vol. 2. Imprimerie de l'Académie impériale des sciences, 1843.